

Eupacannol, a pentacyclic triterpene of a new skeletal type, and other chemical constituents from *Eupatorium cannabinum*^{†‡}

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A pentacyclic triterpene, designated eupacannol (**1**), possessing a new skeletal type, has been isolated from the whole plant of *Eupatorium cannabinum* Linn. (Fam. Asteraceae) in 0.0055% yield. Its structure having a new modified friedlane skeleton has been established as **1** on the basis of ¹H NMR (using paramagnetic shift reagent also) and mass spectral evidence, and chemical studies. β-Myrrin and an anthraquinone derivative physcion have also been isolated. The molecular conformations of eupacannol (**1**) and friedelan-7β-ol (**5**) have been discussed.

As part of our continued studies on Indian *Eupatorium* species^{2,3} we reinvestigated the whole plant of *Eupatorium cannabinum* Linn. (Family : Asteraceae), a shrub of 1–1.5 m height, collected from Darjeeling (altitude ~2400 m). The plant finds application in folk medicine in curing jaundice and scurvy, and in fomenting sores and ulcers⁴.

Earlier investigation on *Eupatorium cannabinum* led to the isolation of a germacranolide – eupatoriopicrin⁵, quercetin⁶, caffeic acid⁶, chlorogenic acid⁶, ascorbic acid⁶, cholin⁶, ferulic acid⁶, α-eupaterol acetate⁷ and euparin⁷.

From the cold chloroform extract of the whole plant we earlier reported² the isolation of dammaradienyl acetate, taraxasterol and stigmasterol, characterized on the basis of their spectral and chemical evidence. The fourth compound isolated from the same extract turned out to be a new saturated pentacyclic triterpene alcohol and has been designated eupacannol⁸ (yield 0.0035%), C₃₀H₅₂O (M⁺ 423), m.p. 265–266°, [α]_D +34 (CHCl₃). Based on spectral properties and chemical evidence the structure of eupacannol has been elucidated as **1**.

The IR spectrum of **1** showed the presence of a hydroxyl group [ν_{max}(KBr) ~3450 cm⁻¹] which is further supported by the presence of a one proton multiplet at δ 3.12 (CHOH) in its ¹H NMR spectrum. In addition, presence of eight methyl groups (24H) was apparent from overlapping signals between δ 0.86–1.24. Chemical evidence in favour of this hydroxyl group was provided by the formation of a monoacetate, eupacannol acetate (**2**), (only under drastic con-

dition, Ac₂O/fused NaOAc, reflux, 3 h), C₃₂H₅₄O₂ (M⁺ 470), m.p. 277–278°. Its ¹H NMR spectrum showed peaks at δ 2.0 (OCOCH₃) and 4.90 (CHOAc), about 1.11 ppm downfield than that of the carbinol methine proton (CHOH) of eupacannol (**1**) supporting the secondary nature of the alcohol. Eupacannol acetate also showed the presence of three tertiary methyl singlets at δ 0.70, 0.81 and 1.16, and overlapping methyl signals (15H) in the region δ 0.90–1.00. The highly hindered nature of the alcoholic OH group was evident from its inert nature, since **1** remained unchanged on treatment with Ac₂O/Py at r.t. for 48 h.

Upon oxidation with CrO₃/Py eupacannol (**1**) furnished the ketone, eupacannone (**3**), C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426), m.p. 245°, [α]_D -25.3 (CHCl₃), ν_{max}(KBr) 1716 cm⁻¹ (6-membered saturated ketone), thus confirming the secondary nature of the hydroxyl group present in **1**. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **3** showed the presence of three secondary methyl groups appearing at δ 0.89 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 0.93 (3H, d, J 8 Hz) and 1.01 (3H, d, J 6 Hz) along with five tertiary methyl groups at δ 0.74 (3H, s), 1.02 (6H, s), 1.06 (3H, s) and 1.19 (3H, s). Eupacannone (**3**) did not react with NaBH₄ in methanol (r.t., overnight), but on refluxing (12 h) with LiAlH₄ in THF was reduced to regenerate **1**. It also failed to produce its hydrazone derivative. Thus the non-reactivity of **3** towards NaBH₄ and hydrazine, and formation of only **1** on reduction with LiAlH₄ established the fact that the OH group present in **1** is highly hindered and hence must be axial in a crowded environment – a fact also confirmed by the reluctance of **1** to form an acetate under usual condition.

[†]Dedicated to Late Professor S. M. Mukherji, an outstanding organic chemist, a dedicated teacher and educationist.

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Eupacannol (**1**) on sublimation under reduced pressure in presence of anhydrous KHSO_4 yielded the corresponding dehydro compound, eupacannene (**4**), $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}$ ($M^+ 410$), m.p. 151° , $[\alpha]_D -6.2$ (CHCl_3). Its ^1H NMR spectrum displayed the presence of three secondary methyl groups appearing at δ 0.76 (3H, d, J 8 Hz), 0.96 (3H, d, J 4 Hz) and 1.16 (3H, d, J 4 Hz) along with five tertiary methyl groups at δ 0.84 (3H, s), 0.88 (6H, s), 0.94 (3H, s) and 1.02 (3H, s) and only one olefinic proton at δ 5.20 (2H, t, J 5 Hz), indicating the presence of $>\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$ grouping in the molecule.

Eupacannol (**1**) as well as its acetate (**2**) and eupacannone (**3**) do not produce any yellow colour with TNM and lack any $>\text{C}=\text{C}<$ stretching vibration in their IR spectra indicating their completely saturated nature.

Having thus established the site of oxygenation at C-7 eupacannol appeared to have an OH, like that of friedelan-7 β -ol⁹. The nature of the carbon skeleton of **1** was revealed, based primarily upon the mass spectrometric fragmentation pattern of **1** and its derivatives. The fragmentation pattern of **1**, especially the appearance of peaks of significant intensities at m/z 275, 249, 207, 205, 191 and 179 (Table 1) was reminiscent of the fragmentation pattern of friedelane type triterpenoid skeleton¹⁰, carrying the OH at C-7, as stated earlier.

Survey of literature revealed that friedelan-7 β -ol [putranjivol (**5**)] and friedelan-7-one [putranjivone (**6**)] are known as the conversion products of friedelan-3,7-dione [putranjivadiene (**7**)⁹]. Compounds **5** and **6** were prepared by reported reactions⁹ from **7**, isolated by us from the trunk bark of *Putranjiba roxburghii*⁹. A direct comparison of the mass spectra of **1** and **5**, and **3** and **6** showed that the fragmentation patterns of these pairs of compounds resemble each other very closely but differ only in the relative abundance of the pairs (Tables 1–3). This observation is reminiscent of the mass fragmentation behaviour of the following pairs of terpenoids, viz. bauerenol (**8**) and multiflorenol (**9**), and isobauerenol (**10**) and isomultiflorenol (**11**) reported by us¹¹, and α -amyrin (**12**) and β -amyrin¹⁰ (**13**) and the corresponding ketones^{9,11}. The structural difference between the members of each pair lie in the position of the two methyls in ring E. The first member of each pair is having vicinal methyls at C-19 (β -) (*S*) and C-20 (α -) (*R*) configuration, in conformity with their biogenesis, while the other member is having *gem*-dimethyls at C-20. The significant peaks in the mass spectra of eupacannol (**1**) and its derivatives **2** and **3** as well as of friedelan-7 β -ol (**5**) and friedelan-7-one (**6**) are rationalized in Schemes 1 and 2.

On the basis of the above observations and also from the fact that the ^1H NMR spectra of **3** and **4** showed the presence of three secondary methyl groups, eupacannol (**1**) should possess a modified ursane skeleton, or a friedelane skeleton with vicinal methyls at C-19 (β -) and C-20 (α -) instead of *gem*-dimethyls at C-20 as in friedelane. Thus eupacannol (**1**) and its derivatives incorporate a β -methyl at each of C-4 (secondary Me), C-5, C-9, C-14, C-17 and C-19, and an α -methyl at each of C-13 and C-20 with *trans-transoid-trans-transoid-trans-transoid-cis*-configuration of the A-B-C-D-E rings.

Table 1. Significant mass ions and their m/z (% base peak) values of eupacannol (1) and friedelan-7b-ol (5), eupacannone (3) and friedelan-7-one (6), eupacannol acetate (2) and eupacannene (4)

Comps.	1	5	3	6	2	4
Ions						
M ⁺	428 (21)	428 (3)	426 (32)	426 (40)	470 (9)	410 (90)
M ⁺ -CH ₃	413 (22)	413 (2)	411 (6)	411 (10)	455 (7)	305 (33)
M ⁺ -H ₂ O/ M ⁺ -ACOH	410 (22)	410 (14)	-	-	410 (6)	-
<i>a</i>	304 (5)	304 (1)	302 (12)	302 (14)	346 (2)	-
<i>b</i>	275 (39)	275 (3)	273 (17)	273 (13)	317 (16)	257 (14)
<i>c</i>	193 (14)	193 (85)	191 (11)	191 (12)	235 (5)	-
<i>d/e</i>	249 (1)	249 (9)	247 (7)	247 (18)	291 (7)	-

Use of paramagnetic shift reagents :

It was found that in the ¹H NMR spectra of 1 and 2 the signals are bunched together in featureless clusters in the high field region. It was shown that various lanthanide com-

Table 2. Intensities (% base peak) of the common significant mass peaks of 1 and 5, 3 and 6, 2, 4 derivatives

	Fragment ions (m/z)					
	<i>f</i> (207)	<i>g</i> (205)	<i>h</i> (179)	<i>i</i> (218)	<i>j</i> (109)	<i>g</i> -Me + H (191)
1	21	44	33	9	100	31
5	4	13	17	16	88	25
3	2	17	17	12	53	11
6	4	38	8	-	46	12
2	22	23	22	6	77	17
4	4	42	2	100	33	33

plexes¹² produce spectral simplifications in the ¹H NMR spectra of aldehydes, ketones, alcohols, amines and other molecules having a relatively basic lone pair of electrons¹³. The "lanthanide induced shifts" (LIS or Δv_i) are thought to be due to primarily pseudocontact interactions¹⁴ and for any particular molecule at a given temperature are inversely proportional to the cube of the internuclear distance (r_i^{-3}) be-

tween the lanthanide metal and the proton under consideration¹⁵, i.e. $\Delta v_i = K / r_i^3$.

The most commonly used complexes are Eu(fod-*d*)₃, i.e. [tris-(1,1,1,2,2,3,3-heptafluoro-7,7-dimethyl-*d*₆-octane-4,6-dionato-*d*₃)europium III] (14) and Eu(DPM)₃, i.e. [tris-(2,2,6,6-tetramethylheptane-3,5-dionato)europium]. The former reagent is superior for weak Lewis bases and also in terms of solubility (which can be a problem with the DPM analog)¹⁶ but requires greater care in handling because of its extreme sensitivity to moisture.

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The other lanthanide metals used to shift ¹H NMR resonances to lower field are erbium, thulium and ytterbium while complexes of praseodymium, cerium, samarium, terbium and holmium tend to shift resonances to higher field^{17,18}. Various aspects of shift reagents have been discussed in some reviews¹⁹⁻²³ in early seventies.

The proposed structure of eupacannol (1) received further confirmation by comparing the 100 MHz ¹H NMR spectra of eupacannol (1) and putranjivol (5) in CDCl₃ adding Eu(fod-*d*)₃ as the paramagnetic shift reagent. Thus, the spectrum of 5 showed clean singlets for 7 tertiary methyl groups at δ 1.02 (6H, s) and 1.09, 1.22, 1.27, 2.45 and 5.32 (CH₃ at C-5) (3H, s each) and a clean 3H doublet (*J* 5 Hz) for the C-4 secondary methyl group at δ 5.69. Whereas, the spectrum of 1 showed clearly the presence of three secondary methyl groups at δ 1.17 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 1.19 (3H, d, *J* 5 Hz) and 5.78 (3H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH₃ at C-4) along with 5 tertiary methyl groups (3H each) at δ 1.44, 1.59, 1.70, 2.17 and 5.46 (CH₃ at C-5). The tertiary methyl at C-5 and the secondary methyl at C-4 have been significantly deshielded in both the spectra of 1 and 5 due to their proximity to the lanthanide metal Eu complexing with the 7 OH in both compounds.

Biogenesis of eupacannol (1) :

Based on established biogenetic pathways to pentacyclic triterpenes²⁴ the biogenesis of eupacannol may occur from squalene (rather than squalene epoxide) which undergoes specific folding and cyclization by a sequence of planar trans

Table 3. Intensities (% base peak) of the common significant mass peaks of eupacannone (3) and friedelan-7-one (6) McLafferty rearrangement

	Fragment ions (m/z)									
	<i>k</i> (233)	<i>k</i> -Me + H (219)	<i>k</i> -Me (218)	<i>l</i> (221)	<i>l</i> -Me (206)	<i>m</i> (205)	<i>n</i> -Me + H (193)	<i>n</i> -Me (179)	<i>m/z</i> 95 (178)	
3	7	4	12	2	7	16	16	16	1	48
6	11	8	-	4	10	38	100	38	13	100

Scheme 1. Some significant common mass fragments (m/z) of compounds 1 to 6 (vide Tables 1 and 2).

additions to olefinic bonds to form the parent tetracyclic intermediate (dammarenyl cation) (for all pentacyclic triterpenes) under the influence of specific enzymes in plant cells. The latter in turn, as is usual, suffers a series of bond migration, methyl and hydride transfers, all in stereospecific trans manner (cf. ursane skeleton) and biological oxidation at C-7 to produce eupacannol. The allylic oxidation

at C-9 in squalene itself, prior to its cyclization may also take place^{8b}. All reactions take place in genetically controlled and enzymatically catalyzed manner.

Molecular conformation of eupacannol (1) and friedalan-7 β -ol (5) :

We reported¹¹ in 1968 that in bauerenol (8) the rings A, B, C, D and E are in chair, half chair, chair, chair and skew

Scheme 2. Mass fragments (m/z) of **4** and **6** via McLafferty rearrangement (*vide* Table 3).

boat conformations respectively. The ring E attains a skew boat rather than a chair conformation in order to avoid a strong 1,3-diaxial interaction between C-17 and C-19 β -methyls, as well as the severe steric interference between C-13 and C-20 α -methyls [if rings D, E both exist in chair conformation]. Likewise, careful inspection of the Dreiding model of eupacannol (**1**) reveals similar molecular conformation. Thus eupacannol (**1**) possesses chair-chair-chair-chair-skew boat conformation (**1a**), ring E attaining a skew boat conformation rather than chair (**1b**) to avoid the strong steric interactions between C-13 α -methyl and C-20 α -methyl, and the *syn* diaxial interaction between C-17 and C-19 β -methyls as in case of bauerenol¹¹(**8**). Isobauerenol (**10**) also possesses similar skew boat conformation¹¹ of ring E.

It may be mentioned that in order to avoid the strong steric interference between C-13 α -methyl and C-20 α -methyl (in case rings D and E both possess chair conformation) (*cf.* **1b**), and to avoid flagpole-flagpole interaction between C-17 and C-20 β -methyls (when only ring E attains

skew boat conformation) (*cf.* **1a**), both rings D and E attain skew boat conformations (**5a**) in friedelan 7 β -ol (**5**) and other friedelan derivatives having rings A, B and C in chair conformations, as well as in multiflorenol (**9**) having rings A, B and C in chair, half chair and chair conformations¹¹ respectively.

The reinvestigation of the shrub, *E. cannabinum* (1 kg), collected from Darjeeling after several decades led to the isolation of two more constituents, β -amyryn (**13**) and an anthraquinone derivative physcion (**15**) in addition to dammaradienyl acetate, stigmasterol and taraxasterol reported earlier², but unfortunately, eupacannol could not be isolated at all; even its presence could not be detected from the benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate fractions of the main chromatogram (*vide* Experimental). This may be due to ecological factors including season and place of collection and maturity of the plants collected. Later on, our attempts so far, even to collect a fresh supply of plants also met with failure and hence, eupacannol (**1**), being almost exhausted in earlier studies and not available in the present investigation, could not, so far, be subjected to infallible X-ray crystallographic or ¹³C NMR spectral study for unambiguous confirmation of the structure of this saturated pentacyclic triterpene having a new modified friedlane skeleton (E ring like ursane) isolated from Nature for the first time⁸. In order to incorporate ¹³C NMR and/or X-ray crystallographic studies we so long postponed the publication of the important results obtained^{8b} in 1974. These studies may be undertaken in future if eupacannol is isolated again.

Experimental

Melting points (m.ps.) were measured in a Kofler block and are uncorrected. The samples for CH analyses were dried under vacuo at 80° for 10 h. The IR spectra were measured as KBr pellets with a Perkin-Elmer 221-1607 instrument. The UV spectra were recorded in aldehyde-free ethanol on a Varian Techtron Series 634 spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ at 60 MHz by a Varian A-60D spectrometer and at 100 MHz by a Varian HA 100D instrument. The peak for TMS or for CHCl₃ (at δ 7.26) was used as the internal standard. The mass spectra were recorded by a AEI MS-9 spectrometer at 70 eV using direct inlet system. Optical rotations were measured in a Hilger-Watts M-511 microptic photoelectric polarimeter. Light petrol used had b.p. 60–80°. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigen) and TLC analyses were performed on silica gel-G microscopic slides or plates.

Extraction : The air-dried milled whole plant (2 kg) of *Eupatorium cannabinum* was extracted exhaustively with CHCl_3 in a percolator at room temperature. Concentration of the extract under reduced pressure afforded a very thick brown oily mass (~15 g) showing negative Dragendorff's test for alkaloid. The extract was dissolved in minimum amount of CHCl_3 and then chromatographed over silica gel (400 g, 82 cm \times 4 cm) and eluted successively with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity using light petrol, light petrol-benzene (1:1), benzene, benzene-chloroform (1:1), chloroform and then chloroform-methanol (97:3). Thirtysix fractions were collected in 200 ml portions and monitored by running thin layer chromatograms in microscopic slides. The fractions having identical spot were mixed up.

Isolation of eupacannol (1) : The residue from fractions 14-18 eluted with benzene was chromatographed repeatedly over silica gel to afford eupacannol, crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol as small shining plates (yield 0.11 g, 0.0055%), m.p. 264–266°, R_f 0.6 (using chloroform as developer), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 34.2$ (c, 0.31 in CHCl_3) (Found : C, 84.2; H, 12.3. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}$: C, 84.04; H, 12.22%).

Isolation of dammaradienyl acetate, taraxasterol and stigmasterol from early light petrol-benzene (1:1) eluate fractions and benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate early and later fractions respectively were reported².

Isolation of β -amyrin (13) : The yellow gum with a few crystals obtained from the later light petrol-benzene (1:1) eluate fractions was subjected to repeated chromatography to give β -amyrin (13), crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol as fine needles (yield 0.009%), m.p. 198°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 85$: IR; ν_{max} 3340 (OH), 2960, 1380 and 1370 cm^{-1} (gem dimethyl); ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3) 0.78 (3H, s), 0.82 (3H, s), 0.86 (6H, s), 0.93 (3H, s), 0.96 (3H, s), 0.99 (3H, s) and 1.13 (3H, s) [eight tertiary methyl groups], 1.21–1.88 (23H, m, methylene and methane protons), 3.20 (1H, dd, J 6 and 10 Hz, carbinol methine proton), 5.51 (1H, dd, J 3 and 8 Hz, vinyl proton); m/z 426 (M^+).

Isolation of physcion (15) : The later benzene fractions of the main chromatogram on concentration gave a red oil which was subjected to preparative thin layer chromatography using silica gel-G as the adsorbent and benzene-chloroform (1:1) as the developer (two developments) to give crude crystals of physcion, recrystallization of which from methanol afforded orange yellow flakes (yield 0.001%), m.p. 204–206°. It gave positive sodium dithionite test, and produced red colour with aqueous sodium hydroxide and or-

ange red colour with magnesium acetate. λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) in EtOH 257 (4.35), 266 (4.35), 288 (4.36) and 431 (4.20); ν_{max} 3442 (OH), 2910, 1658 (CO), 1632 (CO), 1370 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 2.41 (3H, s, aromatic CH_3), 3.89 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.62 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-7) and 7.30 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-5), 7.01 (1H, bs, $w_{1/2}$ 4 Hz, H-2) and 7.55 (1H, bs, $w_{1/2}$ 4 Hz, H-4), 12.01 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , chelated OH) and 12.21 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , chelated OH).

Action of acetic anhydride and pyridine on eupacannol : A solution of eupacannol (20 mg) in pyridine (1.5 ml) was treated with acetic anhydride (2 ml) and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 h. The cooled reaction mixture was then added to water (20 ml), pyridine was neutralized with 2 N HCl and the solid separated was then extracted with chloroform (3 \times 15 ml). The chloroform layer was washed with aqueous sodium chloride solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to yield unchanged eupacannol crystallizing in shining plates (16 mg) from chloroform-petrol, identified by m.m.p., co-TLC and IR spectral studies.

Eupacannol acetate (2) : A mixture of eupacannol (20 mg), acetic anhydride (1.5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (10 mg) was refluxed for 3 h under anhydrous condition. The reaction mixture was cooled, added to water (20 ml) and the oil formed was decomposed by neutralization (pH 7) with sodium bicarbonate. It was then extracted with chloroform (3 \times 15 ml); the combined chloroform extract was washed, dried and concentrated as usual. The brown residue thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the chromatogram with light petrol yielded a white solid, crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol as needles (15 mg), m.p. 277–278° (Found : C, 81.70; H, 11.72. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.64; H, 11.56%).

Eupacannone (3) : A pyridine-chromic acid complex, prepared by adding chromium trioxide (40 mg) in pyridine (2 ml) at 0°, was added dropwise to an ice-cold solution of eupacannol (30 mg) in pyridine (2 ml). The whole mixture was stirred and kept at room temperature for 12 h. It was then added to water (40 ml); the mixture was neutralized with 2 N HCl and extracted with chloroform (3 \times 15 ml). The whole chloroform extract was first washed with water and then with saturated sodium sulphite solution (3 \times 20 ml) and was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extract after evaporation of the solvent was chromatographed over silica gel. The light petrol-benzene (1:1) eluate of the chromatogram furnished a white solid crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol as fine needles (18 mg), m.p. 245°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 25.3$ (c, 0.23 in CHCl_3) (Found : C, 84.24; H, 11.70.

Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%.

Action of hydrazine hydrate on eupacannone : Eupacannone (10 mg) in pyridine (3 ml) containing 99% hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) and conc. HCl (6 drops) was refluxed for an hour. The whole mixture was added to water (15 ml), pyridine was neutralized with 2 N HCl and extracted with chloroform (3×10 ml). The chloroform layer after usual washing and drying was concentrated to give only unchanged eupacannone (9 mg).

Attempted sodium borohydride reduction of eupacannone : Eupacannone (10 mg) was dissolved in dry methanol (15 ml) and to it sodium borohydride (20 mg) was added. The whole mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. It was then added to water (50 ml), the solution was neutralized with 2 N HCl and extracted with chloroform (3×15 ml). The chloroform layer was washed, dried as usual and concentrated. The residue (9 mg) was crystallized to give unchanged eupacannone (m.m.p., co-TLC, IR).

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of eupacannone to eupacannol : To a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (60 mg) in 5 ml of dry tetrahydrofuran a solution of eupacannone (30 mg) in tetrahydrofuran (6 ml) was added dropwise at 5° with continuous stirring. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature and was then refluxed for further 12 h. The cooled reaction mixture after addition of ethyl acetate (4 ml) was stirred for ½ h, and then ice-cold 2 N H_2SO_4 (12 ml) was added to it. The whole mixture was refluxed for 1 h, cooled and extracted with chloroform (10 ml×3). The chloroform extract, showing a single spot in TLC, was washed and dried as usual and concentrated to furnish a white solid (25 mg) crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in small plates, m.p. 264–266°, found to be identical with eupacannol in all respects (m.m.p., co-TLC, IR).

Eupacannene (4) : Eupacannol (30 mg) and fused potassium bisulphate (60 mg) were thoroughly mixed up in a sublimation tube. The mixture was heated and sublimed under reduced pressure. The sublimed mass was extracted from the sublimation tube with chloroform (30 ml). Removal of the solvent furnished a yellow mass which on chromatography over silica gel afforded a white solid (20 mg) from the light petrol eluate. The solid mass crystallized from chloroform-light petrol in fine needles, m.p. 151°, $[\alpha]_D -6.2$ (c, 0.25 in $CHCl_3$) and was characterized as eupacannene (4) (Found : C, 87.63; H, 12.10. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{50}$: C, 87.73; H, 12.27%) .

Attempted hydrogenation of eupacannene : A solution of eupacannene (10 mg) in absolute ethanol was stirred in an atmosphere of hydrogen, in presence of PtO_2 for 4 h. The solution was filtered and evaporated under reduced pres-

sure to give only the unchanged eupacannene (9 mg).

Isolation of putranjivadiolone (7) : Air-dried powdered trunk bark of *Putranjiva roxburghii* Wall. (1 kg) was extracted exhaustively with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus. Concentration of the extract under reduced pressure afforded a thick brown oily mass which was devoid of any basic constituent. The extract was taken up with benzene and was chromatographed over activated alumina (250 g) and eluted successively with light petrol, light petrol-benzene (1:1), light petrol-benzene (1:4) and benzene. Fifteen fractions were collected in 200 ml portions and were monitored by running thin layer chromatogram. The fractions having identical spots were mixed up. Rechromatography of the residue from light petrol-benzene (1:1) fractions 4-6 afforded only friedelin (friedelan-3-one) while the residue from light-petrol-benzene (1:4) fractions 7-15 on repeated crystallizations from chloroform-light petrol afforded putranjivadiolone (friedelan-3,7-dione), $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$ (M^+440) (yield 0.1%), m.p. 286–288°, $[\alpha]_D -36$ (c, 0.25 in $CHCl_3$).

Friedelan-7-one (6) : Putranjivadiolone (7) (200 mg) in ethylene glycol (80 ml) was refluxed with 99% hydrazine hydrate (3 ml) for 4 h. Potassium hydroxide (200 mg) solution in ethylene glycol (5 ml) was added to it and the solution was refluxed for a further period of 6 h after which the condenser was removed and the temperature was raised to 190°. After refluxing for an additional period of 2 h, the reaction mixture was cooled, added to water (500 ml), neutralized with 2 N HCl and extracted with chloroform (3×200 ml). The chloroform layer was washed, dried and concentrated to yield a yellowish mass which on chromatography over activated alumina yielded a solid (150 mg) from the benzene eluate fraction of the chromatogram which crystallized from chloroform-methanol in heavy needles, m.p. 260–262°, $[\alpha]_D +21.5$ and was identified as friedelan-7-one (putranjivone) (6) from its m. p., IR and mass spectra (Found : C, 84.20; H, 11.71. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

Friedelan-7 β -ol (5) : Friedelan-7-one (50 mg) in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran solution (5 ml) was added dropwise to an ice-cold slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (100 mg) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). The whole mixture was then refluxed for 12 h, cooled and to it ethyl acetate (5 ml) was added slowly. The mixture was, stirred for ½ h and then refluxed with 2 N H_2SO_4 (10 ml) for 1 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water and then extracted with chloroform (50 ml×3). Removal of the solvent yielded a yellow mass which was chromatographed. The residue from the benzene eluate fractions crystallized from chloroform-methanol, to yield friedelan-7 β -ol (5) in needles (30 mg), m.p. 245–246°, $[\alpha]_D$

+33.2 (c, 0.27 in CHCl₃) (Found : C, 84.12; H, 12.20. Calcd. for C₃₀H₅₂O : C, 84.04; H, 12.33%).

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References

1. B. Talapatra, G. Das, A. K. Das, K. Biswas and S. K. Talapatra, *Phytochemistry*, 1998, **49**, 1353.
2. S. K. Talapatra, D. S. Bhar and B. Talapatra, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, **27**, 1137.
3. S. K. Talapatra, D. S. Bhar and B. Talapatra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **15**, 806.
4. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayer and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 113.
5. L. Dolejs and A. Herout, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1962, **27**, 2654 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **58**, 10244).
6. F. Pagani and G. Romussi, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, **68**, 46990.
7. J. Grzybowska, Z. Jerzmanowska and H. Witkowski, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, **48**, 12378; J. Grzybowska and Z. Jerzmanowska, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, **48**, 12378.
8. (a) S. K. Talapatra, D. S. Bhar and B. Talapatra, Abstracts, "9th IUPAC Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products", Ottawa, Canada, 1974, p. 39B; (b) D. S. Bhar, Ph.D. Dissertation, Calcutta University, 1974.
9. P. Sengupta, A. K. Chakravarty, A. M. Duffield, L. J. Durham and C. Djerassi, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 1205.
10. H. Budzikiewicz, J. M. Wilson and C. Djerassi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3688.
11. S. K. Talapatra, S. Sengupta and B. Talapatra, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 5963.
12. N. Ahmed, N. S. Bhacca, J. Selbin and J. D. Wander, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 2564 and references cited therein.
13. J. K. Sanders and D. H. Williams, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 641.
14. C. C. Hinckley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 5160.
15. C. C. Hinckley, M. R. Klotz and F. Patil, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 2417.
16. R. E. Rondeau and R. E. Sievers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 1522.
17. D. R. Crump, J. K. Sanders and D. H. Williams, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 4419.
18. J. Briggs, G. H. Frost, F. A. Hart, G. P. Moss and M. L. Staniforth, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 749.
19. R. Von Ammon and R. D. Fischer, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1972, **11**, 675.
20. M. R. Paterson and G. H. Wahl, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1972, **49**, 790.
21. J. K. M. Sanders and D. H. Williams, *Nature*, 1972, **240**, 385.
22. B. C. Mayo, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1973, **2**, 49.
23. A. F. Cockerill, G. L. O. Davies, R. C. Harden and D. M. Rackham, *Chem. Rev.*, 1973, **73**, 553.
24. Paul M. Dewick, "Medicinal Natural Products", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1997.